

LAKBAY-DIWA ✨
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

JANUARY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES of EXPRESSION *A Creative Folio*

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue I (January 2026), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

ANGELA DOMINIQUE T. LOMAGDONG, PhD

Faculty Teacher

University of Eastern Philippines

University Town, Catarman, Northern Samar

Region VIII, Philippines

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18502682

Treasures Beneath the Nation's Roots

Before the travellers came from the seas
They were already here as old as the tree
With goddess guiding, with arts of their own
Their culture was planted the spirit had grown.

They are often overlooked, forgotten and rejected
Not knowing the gifts, they once had reflected
Discriminated against, judged, and feared
These are the burden their voices have seared.

The origin of the nation came from them
They are very promising though rarely seen
Staying in rivers, mountains, and fields so green
Living in fishing, hunting and planting trees.

Their lives flow in simple, carried by the breeze
Some are known for the shade of their skin
Some by their teeth, or the pain within
Different beauty, great diversities
This makes the country famed overseas.

Clothes with patterns, colors so bright
Symbols of cultures, pride, and might
Curly hair, pierced tongue, brave and true
Aetas, Igorot, Mangyan and Lumad too
Different groups but one in stand
United in spirit across the land.

Water from above, they will just dance
Abundant plants bring nature's chance
Whistling in hunts, herbs for medicine
Walking long miles, that's how they live.

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue I (January 2026), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

Indigenous people fought for their lands
The only true wealth that stayed in their hands
Their treasure, their happiness and their life
Yet stolen away through injustice and strife.

Mining destroyed the homes they knew
Their silence enforced, their numbers become few
Blinded by greed, reckless deeds they pursue
What our ancestors cherished is now deemed and doomed
But still, they hope and still pray to guard their heritage.

I once heard their laughter echoing through the trees
In the land once where the nation begins
A wealth they behold passed down from within
A strength that endures through longing and grief.

May we protect their land and name
And keep their stories with burning flame
For in their strength we clearly see
The beauty of life in simplicity.